

But this I say...

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When life has brought you to see day and night
 It is twinned with endless struggles and bold fight
 But this I say, traverse this chaotic world boldly
 Remember, your generations have brought you steadily
 Not to be conquered and be pitiful and woeful
 But to be victorious in battles, even in the grievous fall

When life has been so weary and doubtful
 And all the stars connive to let you mournful
 But this I say, you must go on unhurriedly
 Set your eyes straight to the peak of your destiny
 You may stumble, you may fall, but this should I say
 Never surrender to life's circumstances and adversity

This expedition called life is like sailing against giant waves
 Full of danger and the unfathomable depth of knaves
 But this I say, keep sailing to the unknown
 Cause life does not progress in your comfort zone
 You must be like a pirate, however, "ahoy" to the treasure
 Endure the toughness of this voyage full of pressure

Some current will pull you down, some will toss you up
 The harshness of the world will make you give-up
 But this I say, play along in the vastness of the universe
 You may face the fierceness of the world's vastness
 Trust yourself, trust the process until you reach the finish line
 After all, life is ephemeral, fleeting, and will end in the ground line

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